

TEACHING SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION WITH INFORMATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: *Professional interpreter training has been one of the main topics in the field of interpreting studies. In fact, it can be said that an initial impetus for interpreting research derived from educators need for a systematic. In this article I want to delve into introduce IT methods in teaching simultaneous translation.*

Keywords: *Interpretation, simultaneous interpretation, target language (TL), source language (SL).*

Introduction

Interpretation or interpreting is the facilitating of oral or sign-language to the communication, either simultaneously or consecutively, between users of different languages. Translation studies is the systematic study of the theory, description and application of interpretation and translation. An interpreter is a person who converts a thought or expression in a source language into an expression with a comparable meaning in a target language either simultaneously in “real time” or consecutively after one party has finished speaking. The interpreter's function is to convey every semantic element (tone and register) and every intention and feeling of the message that the source-language speaker is directing to target-language recipients. [4;2022.]

Main Part

Translators have time to consider and revise each word and sentence before delivering their product to the client. While live interpretation's goal is to achieve total accuracy at all times, details of the original (source) speech can be missed and interpreters can ask for clarification from the speaker. In any language, including sign languages, when a word is used for which there is no exact match, expansion may be necessary in order to fully interpret the intended meaning of the word (ex: the English word “hospitable” may require several words or phrases to encompass its complex meaning). Another unique situation is when an interpreted message appears much shorter or longer than the original message. The message may appear shorter at times because of unique efficiencies within a certain language. [1; 2006].

In (extempore) simultaneous interpretation (SI), the interpreter renders the message in the target-language as quickly as he or she can formulate it from the source language, while the source-language speaker continuously speaks; an oral-language SI interpreter, sitting in a sound-proof booth, speaks into a microphone,

while clearly seeing and hearing the source-language speaker via earphones. The simultaneous interpretation is rendered to the target-language listeners via their earphones. Moreover, SI is the common mode used by sign language interpreters, although the person using the source language, the interpreter and the target language recipient (since either the hearing person or the deaf person may be delivering the message) must necessarily be in close proximity. [3; 2016].

The first introduction and employment of extempore simultaneous interpretation using electronic equipment that can facilitate large numbers of listeners was the Nuremberg Trials, with four official working languages.

Finding solutions to dilemmas is a constant in the work of the translator. This includes translating problems such as linguistic or cultural “untranslatability”, being able to manage losses and gains, solutions to lexical ambiguity, etc., through various mechanisms such as compensation, loans, explanatory notes, adaptation, equivalence, paraphrasing, analogies, etc.

Translators should also be aware that meaning is not only conveyed by words. Hence adequate decoding and re-coding of nomenclatures, figures, tables and charts; standardized terms, acronyms, metonyms, toponyms, etc. is a matter that must be properly considered.

A good translator should define some essential starting-points for the approximation to a text to be translated, such as the author of the text, the aim of the text, the readership, and the standard to be used, for which it is important to identify and categorize the author, the message, the kind of discourse, the translator and the readership.

Another important aspect is the pre-editing of the original text to detect eventual source text defects, on the one hand, and the post-editing of the translated text to verify the use of the most adequate syntactic, semantic and graphemic levels (recognition of the reviser’s role), on the other hand.

Among formal matters, translators should be aware of and control the sound effect and cadence of the translated text (“translating with the ear”) to avoid cacophonous combinations and calque on the source language. [5;76-80].

Last, but not least, translators should observe that the essence—in terms of meaning and sense, register and style, etc.—and the lay out of the original text—in terms of format, i.e. sources, paragraphs, indentation, columns, tables, etc.—is properly adhered to in the translated unit.

My experience in the field of translation training has given me some useful hints on how to elaborate a translation methodology with undergraduate students who want to become translators. This approach attempts to develop some workshop activities

for the translation process—as a cooperative activity with the students—through a graded and sequential procedure. We must assume that students have sound linguistic knowledge, both theoretical and practical, and a wide cultural bilingual background, achieved during their first years in college.

This methodology, consisting of a step-by-step procedure workshop, (stages may sometimes be sequential and successive, sometimes, alternated) has proven quite successful in my classes in terms of students' motivation, productivity and the quality of their work. However, I do think that this methodology can be improved.

The teacher makes a selection of the material to be translated. Texts must be chosen according to previously defined objectives for translation practice, taking into account the degree of difficulty of the texts (semantic, cultural, stylistic, etc.), the topic or the specific knowledge area (science and technology; social, institutional, economic and/or political topics; and literary or philosophical works), the translation problems to be solved, and so on.

After browsing through the text (scan reading and/or skim reading), the students, assisted by their teacher, should identify the source, the norm, the type of text, the register, the style and the readership of the text selected. It is a kind of game of the imagination in which the text is real but the client and her/his needs are imaginary.

The students should read the whole text at least twice: The first reading will be comprehensive and general, to become acquainted with the topic and to understand the original, always bearing in mind that meaning is context-determined.

The second reading must be a “deep” reading, placing emphasis on items where translation problems may appear. In other words, this is what I have called “reading with translation intention”, i.e. doing pre-editing and assessing the quality of the writing. In my opinion, when translating into the TL, if the translator detects mistakes (usually due to misprints) in the original text, s/he should be entitled to amend them in her/his version if too obvious or else consult the client or an expert in case of doubt. When doing this “reading with translation intention,” students should first underline unknown terms and then they should mentally confront potential translation difficulties in the text with suitable translation procedures. [2;89]

The teacher then divides the text into as many segments as students in the group. Depending on the degree of difficulty and the length of the text, these segments may be paragraphs, columns, pages or even whole chapters. Then, each student is assigned a fair portion of the text. The segment distribution order should rotate so that a different student begins a translation unit every time.

If the topic is already quite familiar to the students, they do a preliminary translation. As this is the first approach to the text, it will probably lack naturalness,

since students tend to transfer SL units of translation to TL units of translation (“one-to-one translation”). This first approach can often be made orally and suggested annotations may be written in the margins. [7;1988]

If the topic is completely unknown to the students, they should consult complementary literature. In other words, before beginning the transfer process, they should resort to various documentation sources, especially parallel texts (those which are similar in nature and style) in the language of the original. This allows them to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Once the “one-to-one” version is accomplished, the students do a second version of their own translation - this time a written draft is handling the most suitable translation strategies and procedures and being faithful in the transfer of ideas.

With the original text in front of her/him and being careful to follow the same correlative order of the SL text, each student reads out her/his own version of the translated text, making the necessary pauses between sentences.

During this procedure, the students and the teacher need to set up all necessary conventions with regard to the homogeneity of the terms and the coherence and cohesion of the final version.

As Newmark states, “*translation is for discussion*”. Students should then be encouraged to take notes and discuss the (in)convenience of the contributions and comments arising from this analytical reading of each one of the different versions proposed. [8;1995]

As a metacognitive activity, the students, assisted by the teacher, analyze the translation strategies and procedures used, and discuss the reasons taken into account in the choice of each analyzed criterion: “The ability to discuss translations in an objective way is central to a translator’s competence”, [3;1995].

The students hand in the final version of their revised and post-edited segments, which have already been amended in the light of the whole text. The work must be typed, double-spaced and paged according to the original.

The teacher makes a final revision (second post-edit), gives formative evaluation and makes comments, emphasizes findings, “happy” solutions and creative acts, on the one hand, and analyzes failures and weaknesses in the process, on the other.

In seminars of this kind, I assume that the teacher is understood as a facilitator of the translation task, since the lion's share of the transfer process is accomplished by the students, mainly collectively, but also individually. I therefore consider it valid for students to consult all possible information sources, including the traditional written forms, the “live” sources or informants, e.g. their own teacher (the “client”, in

this case), experts in the topic, native speakers, translation software, term data bases and the international data processing nets.

In sum, translators must understand the original text, for which they must have wide general knowledge, handle the vocabulary of the topic in the SL as well as in the target language (TL) and, last but not least, write their own language well. [9; pp56].

Conclusion

Some strategy applied by the translator in his translation (translation technique) are presented. These techniques are implemented to solve untranslatability. By introducing these techniques, the students improve their translation competence, especially in translating untranslatable words or expression. Students' responses on the materials related the translation theory are also presented. This will be useful input for future improvement for the translation subject.

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